

ANALYSIS OF SINGKARAK LAKE TOURISM DEVELOPMENT TO INCREASE THE COMPETITIVENESS AND THE REGIONAL ORIGINAL INCOME AT INDONESIA

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Abstract

This research explores the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of various tourism objects around Singkarak Lake. It also aims to develop the appropriate strategies to increase the capacity of these objects and their cluster types. The inductive statistics, SWOT analysis, and Hierarchical Cluster methods were used to explore the objects, analyze their capacity, and a development strategy. The Inductive statistics results showed 6 clusters of tourism objects consisting of 19, 16, 17, 18, 17, and 9 for natural, cultural, religious, historical, culinary, and craft tourism objects, respectively. The SWOT analysis explained that quadrants I (strong and likely), II (diversification-combination), and III (Turn Around and Stability) are occupied by natural and culinary-craft, cultural, and religious-historical tourism objects, respectively. Furthermore, the strategy of developing them is by using Strength Opportunities, Strength-Threads, and Weak-Opportunities. Finally, the Hierarchical Cluster results showed that the western, eastern, northern, and southern areas of Singkarak Lake contained natural, culinary and craft, cultural as well as religious and historical tourism objects.

Keywords: Development Strategy; Regional Original Income; SWOT Analysis; Tourism Objects

INTRODUCTION

Tourism destinations need to be able to create satisfying services for consumers and compete effectively at local, regional, and global levels. The right strategy is to recognize oneself and the environment from the strengths possessed and utilizes opportunities to realize weaknesses and face existing challenges. According to Purnomo and Zulkieflimansyah (2007), the tourism industry needs to develop strategies against new trends to achieve and maintain its competitive position. A tourism destination's success depends on the availability of attractive tourism objects and easy access to these facilities and infrastructure. This industry increases economic growth by providing income through employment opportunities, thereby enhancing the living standards of the host community (Wahab, 2003). Some of the factors capable of influencing the development of the national tourism industry are natural, cultural, religious, historical, culinary, and craft. Presently, several communities are unable to boost their economy through tourism due to their inability to properly manage these objects, lack of instructions on existing objects, and minimal role of local governments. Therefore, this research aims to determine the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of natural, cultural, religious, historical, culinary, and craft tourism objects around Singkarak Lake. It also aims to develop the appropriate strategies to increase the capacity of these objects and determine their cluster types.

This research's significance is related to the following: (1) Development of Singkarak Lake Tourism by the Solok and Tanah Datar Regency Governments in accordance with Regional

Regulation Number 4 of 2013 concerning the Master Plan for Regional Tourism Development of Solok Regency in 2013-2025; (2) Development of Lake Tourism by the West Sumatra Government in West Sumatra Province following Regional Regulation Number 3 of 2014 on the Master Plan for Tourism Development of West Sumatra Province in 2014-2025; and iii.) Strategic Plan for the Development of Lake Tourism in line with the Minister of Tourism Regulation Number 29 of 2015. According to the theory of income from the regional tourism industry, a tourist attraction is anything unique, beautiful, and valued in the form of diversified natural, cultural, environmental, and artificial wealth, which becomes the sole purpose of tourist visits, thereby increasing the income and economic growth of the community (Koen Mayers, 2009). Singkarak is the second largest lake on Sumatra Island after Toba in North Sumatra, with an area of 107.8 km². The lake, the headwaters of the Batang Ombilin River, has become the center of an international bicycle racing tour known as the Tour de Singkarak. Furthermore, this lake is located on the Sumatran crossing, with railroad tracks on both sides adorning its shores. It is also beautified by the existence of a hydroelectric tunnel (PLTA), the natural stunning green hill panorama, and the water clarity of the beaches, thereby making it one of the destinations for Regional, National, and International tourists. Singkarak Lake is located in the administrative area of Solok and Tanah Datar Regency Governments consisting of four sub-districts, namely Junjung Sirih, X Koto Singkarak, Rambatan, and South Batipuh. These sub-districts comprises of nineteen villages, including Paninggahan, Muaro Pingai, Sandiang Baka, Sumani, Koto Sani, Singkarak, Aripin, Kacang, Tikalak, Tanjung Alai, Balimbing, Rambatan, Padang Magek, Simawang, Tigo Koto, Sumpur, Batu Taba, Guguk Malalo, and Padang Laweh Malalo.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Tourism Industry

According to W. Hunziker and Yoeti (1994), tourism enterprises are all business entities that combine various means of production to provide goods and services of a special tourism nature. Tourism objects and attractions are important elements in this industry, which can succeed in preserving natural and cultural facilities and infrastructure, as well as culinary and craft tourism, objects sellable to tourists (Suwena, Widyatmaja 2010).

Tourism Object Development

Several approaches are used to conduct tourism development, namely community involvement in the planning process and regional carrying capacity, economic industrial approach, emphasizing social and environmental goals, while making visitor satisfaction level the main target. Others include physical, community, and sustainable spatial approaches, in accordance with geographic land use, maximum community involvement in the tourism development process, and economic development's impact on the environment, respectively (B Rusyidi, M Fedryansah 2018).

Integrated Tourism

Integrated tourism is a concept used to ensure tourists enjoy their stay by providing unique tourist objects (Suharso 2009). The development of an integrated tourism area is conducted by considering tourist activity centers, characteristics of tourism objects, and providing links with routes (Pelupessy, Julia, Prescella, 2011). It is necessary to develop a core zone, concentrated with objects as the center of tourist attractions. This zone should have accommodation, various information centers, and other facilities that support tourism activities. Empirical studies with the theme "Tourism development in Indonesia" have been conducted in Indonesia, including Adityaji, R. (2018) with the title "Formulation of a Tourism Destination Development Strategy Using the SWOT Analysis Method: A Case Study of the Kapasan Chinatown Area in Surabaya; Ildha N. Maiwa (2016) titled "Management of Tourism Destinations by the Solok Regency Government in 2014-2015 (Study of Singkarak Lake Tourism Objects)"; Emelia, Fitri (2009) titled "Alternative Use of Lake for Tourism Development through the Aquatic and Fishery Resource Sustainability Concept in the Singkarak Lake"; and Yudin Citriadin, and Yunita Marlina (2020) with the title "Collaborative Management of Natural Tourism in Dompu Regency."

METHODS

This descriptive quantitative research was carried out to identify tourism objects with SWOT (Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, and Threat) analysis. SWOT is an analytical tool that examines and records internal (strengths and weaknesses) and external (opportunities and threats) strategic factors and translates them into value.

Tourism object clusters are determined using quartile and Hierarchical Cluster analysis techniques (Coman A. and B. Ronen 2009). The Hierarchical method is a clustering technique used to form a hierarchy based on a certain level. Therefore, it resembles a tree structure with the process conducted in stages.

Population and Sample

Primary qualitative data obtained through Focus Group Discussions (FGD), Questionnaires, and Interviews were used to conduct this research. These data were further strengthened using quantitative data from the tourism office of West Sumatra Province, Solok Regency, and Tanah Datar Regency. The population used is the Singkarak Lake tourism area with 19 villages, namely Paninggahan, Muaro Pingai, Sandiang Baka, Sumani, Koto Sani, Singkarak, Aripin, Tikalak, Kacang, Tanjung Alai, Sumpur, Batu Taba, Guguk Malalo, Koto Laweh Malalo, Simawang, Rambatan, Balimbing, Padang Magek, and Tigo Koto. These villages are located in 4 sub-districts in Solok and Tanah Datar Regencies, West Sumatra Province, Indonesia. The sample consists of 20 respondents in each sub-population group, namely tourism visitors, local government, communities, and tourism actors. The number of samples and population is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Number and Group of Respondents in Filling out Questionnaires and Research Interviews

No	Respondent Group	Respondent Sample	Number of Villages	Number of Samples
1	Tourism Visitors	20	19	380
2	Local Government	20	19	380
3	Local Communities	20	19	380
4	Local Tourism Actors	20	19	380
	Total			1.520

Source: Processed Data, 2021

Model

The following analytical model was used to conduct this research:

1. Inductive Statistical Analysis was carried out from facts in the field using a bottom-up approach to identify research objects without existing idealistic ideas (Glaser, B.G. and Strauss, A.L. 2006).
2. SWOT analysis was used to identify various factors systematically to formulate a corporate strategy based on the logic capable of maximizing strengths and opportunities while simultaneously minimizing weaknesses and threats (Freddy Rangkuti, 2017). This type of analysis also consists of the IFAS (Internal Factor Analysis Summary) and EFAS (External Factor Analysis Summary) matrix methods.

a. Tourism Object Position

IFAS and EFAS tables were used to determine the position of tourism objects with X and Y axes graphs. IFAS table was used to evaluate the difference between the total value of the strength and weakness factors on the X-axis. Meanwhile, EFAS table analyzed the difference between the total value of the opportunity and threat factors on the Y-axis. The location of Quadrant I, II, III, or IV will determine the position of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of each tourism object. Quadrants I, II, III, and IV use Rapid Growth-Oriented, Survival Turn Around, Aggressive Maintenance, and Diversification strategies, respectively.

b. Tourism Object Development Strategy

Determination of the right strategy for developing tourism objects is based on the analysis results of IFAS and EFAS tables using the Strength-Opportunity, Weak-Opportunity, Strength-Thread, and Weakness-Thread strategies as shown in the SWOT matrix (Table2).

Table 2: Analysis Results of IFAS and EFAS

IFAS EFAS	Strength (S)	Weakness (W)
Opportunity (O)	S-O Strategy (I) A strategy that uses strengths and takes advantage of opportunities	W-O Strategy (III) A strategy that minimizes weaknesses and takes advantage of opportunities
Threat (T)	S-T Strategy (II) A strategy that uses strengths and overcomes threats	W-T Strategy (IV) A strategy that minimizes weaknesses and avoids threats

3. Hierarchical Cluster and Quartile Analyses

Hierarchical cluster is a multivariate analysis technique used to group objects based on their characteristics and cluster homogenous observation data into groups. This process is based on the similarity in the contribution scores of each object using the output description of Quartile Analysis (Wahyuningsi Nuri et al., 2013).

The agglomerative hierarchical cluster analysis uses a complete linkage technique that combines data according to the distance between the furthest members. The following is an agglomerative hierarchical cluster algorithm:

1. Calculate the distance matrix. The distance used with the Euclidean Distance Formula is shown as follows:

$$d_{ij} = \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^p (x_{ik} - x_{jk})^2}$$

Description:

d_{ij} : distance between object i and j

x_{ik} : value of object i on k – th variabele

x_{jk} : value of object j on k – th variable

p : number of variables observed

2. Combine the two closest clusters. If the distance between objects a and b has the smallest value compared to other objects in the Euclidean distance matrix, then the combination of the two clusters in the first stage is d_{ab} .
3. Update the distance matrix according to the agglomerative method clustering technique. If d_{ab} is the closest distance from the Euclidean distance matrix, then the formula for the agglomerative method is as follows:

$$d_{(ab)c} = \min \{d_{a,c}; d_{b,c}\}$$

Single linkage
formula

$$d_{(ab)c} = \text{average} \{d_{a,c}; d_{b,c}\}$$

Average linkage formula

$$d_{(ab)c} = \max \{d_{a,c}; d_{b,c}\}$$

Complete linkage formula

4. Repeat steps 2 and 3 until only one cluster remains
5. Create a dendrogram

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

Finding

1. Singkarak Lake Tourism Object Clustering

Based on the results of inductive statistical analysis and exploration, Singkarak Lake tourism objects are divided into 6 clusters, as shown in Table 3:

Table 3: Singkarak Lake Tourism Objects

No	Singkarak Lake Tourism Objects					
	Natural Tourism	Cultural Tourism	Religious Tourism	Historical Tourism	Culinary Tourism	Craft Tourism
1	Gaugauan Peak and Ahmad Sadin Paninggahan Peak	Batagak Panguluk Datuk Kaum Tradition	Old Surau in Rimbo Hulu Paninggahan	Dutch Quinine Gardens at Rinbo Lasi	Pangek, curry, and Sasau fried side dishes	Pandan Woven Mat
2	Ngalau Tabing Paninggahan	Marak Muaro Pulai-Anak Daro Tradition	Tomb of Angku Junjung Sirih Paninggahan	Dutch coffee plantation at Rimbo Hulu Paninggahan	Pangek, curry, and Bilih fried side dishes	Mansiang Woven Prayer Mat
3	Alahan Muaro River to Catch Bilih Fish	Anak Dijapui Bako Tradition	Tomb in Sandiang Baka's House	Dutch Beo Building, Sandiang Baka	Curry and Palai Rinuk side dishes	Unjui Pandan
4	Junjung Sirih Springs	Mandudukan Nyinyik Mamak Baralek Traditional Speech	Tuo Nagari Padang Magek Mosque	Kamba Tigo Waterwheel on the Ombilin River	Rendang Padang	Kampie Mansiang
5	Gobah Hill	Caranao Batirai Bungo Ameh Tradition containing betel, areca nut, sadah, and gambier	Tomb of Sheikh Angku Duo Baleh Guguk Malalo	Singkarak Lakeside Railway Station	Chopped Curry and Gajeboh	Wallets, Pandan Mansiang Woven Bags
6	Batang Lembang Muoro River	Turun Mandi Anak	Turun Mandi Anak Baru Lahir	Singkarak Lake Side Railroad	Goat Curry	Mattresses and Pillows from Kapuh
7	Setu Ujung Ladang Koto Sanai	Sarunai Flute	Children's Aqiqah	Traditional Hall and Village Hall	Sticky Rice Lemang	Clay Jugs and Talenang
8	Cinangkik Peak	Randai	Birthday of Prophet Muhammad	Nagari Hall	Abuk Cake	Sinaeh Rope
9	Tikalak Beach	Plate Dance	Sacrificial Animal Slaughtering	Pasangerahan Singkarak	Garubik and Golok-golok	Unjui sampayo

10	Singkarak Paragliding Hill	Traditional Silat	Islamic New Year	Bagonjong Gadang House	Tungkuih-Tungkuih	
11	Kacang Ateh Peak	Sewah Dance	Eid Al-Adha	Surau and Mosque	Lapek Bugih cake	
12	Tanjung Alai Panorama	Indang Dance	Eid Al-Fitr	Singkarak Lake hydroelectric power plant (PLTA)	Sunsulung cake	
13	Sumpur Resort Enchantment	Talempong and Gandang	Ramadan month fasting	Rambatan Livestock Market	Boiled rice cake	
14	Tanjung Mutiara White Sand Beach	Tabuh	Recitation at the Place of the Dead	Village Tradition Density	Amping	
15	Makau Duo Peak	Saluang	Mangaji Kasurau	Sumpur Restaurant	Galau-Galau	
16	Palano Stone Natural Charm	Rabab	Musabakah Telewatil Quran (MTQ)	Rimbo Ulu Paninggahan Revolution Trail	Black sticky rice tapai	
17	Aur Duri Tigo Koto Peak		Lailatul Qadar	Medan Nan Paneh	Eel Curry	
18	Sumpur River Rafting			Lubang Jepang Cave in Padang Belimbing, Koto Sani		
19	Koto Sani Hot Spring					

Source: research in 2020

Therefore, it can be concluded that this lake has 19, 16, 17, 18, 17 and 9 of natural, cultural, religious, historical, culinary, and craft tourism objects, respectively.

2. Space SWOT Matrix Analysis

The SWOT matrix analysis results are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Space SWOT Matrix for Singkarak Lake Tourism Objects

Based on the IFAS Matrix, it can be explained as table 4:

Table 4: The SWOT Matrix Analysis Results

Quadrant	Strength	Weakness	Difference between strength and weakness factor values	Opportunity	Threat	Difference between opportunity and threat factor values	Quadrant	Results
Singkarak Lake Natural Tourism	22,181	0,9300	1,2881 (X)	23,539	11,359	1,2180(Y)	I [1,2881 ; 1,2180]	Natural tourism objects are in a strong position and have the opportunity to develop
Cultural Tourism	20,262	0,8365	1,1897(X)	0,7124	22,812	-1,5688(Y)	II [1,5688 ; -1,1897]	Cultural tourism objects are in a strong position and have threats
Religious and Historical Tourism	10,232	23,848	-1,3616 (X)	2,8579	0,4256	2,4323(Y)	III [2,0870 ; 2,4323]	Religious and historical tourism objects are in a weak position and have the opportunity to develop.
Culinary and Craft Tourism	22,652	0,6320	1,6332(X)	22,058	0,7225	1,4833(Y)	I [1,6332 ; 1,4833]	Culinary and Craft tourism objects are in a strong position and have the opportunity to develop.

3. Analysis of the Strategy for the Development of Singkarak Lake Tourism Objects

The SWOT analysis results in the development strategy of Singkarak Lake tourism objects are described in Table 5:

Table 5: Combination of SWOT Matrix Strategies for Singkarak Lake Tourism Objects

IFAS EFAS	Strength (S)	Weakness (W)
Natural Tourism Objects		
Opportunity (O)	I) S-O Strategy (Aggressive) $2,2181 + 2,3539 = 4,572$	III) W-O Strategy (Turn-Around) $0,9300 + 2,3539 = 3,2839$
Thread (T)	II) S-T Strategy (Diversification) $2,2181 + 1,1359 = 3,354$	IV) W-T Strategy (Defensive) $0,9300 + 1,1359 = 2,0659$
Cultural Tourism Objects		
Opportunity (O)	(I) S-O Strategy (Aggressive) $2,0262 + 0,7124 = 2,7386$	(III) W-O Strategy (Turn-Around) $0,8365 + 0,7124 = 1,5489$
Thread (T)	(II) S-T Strategy (Diversification) $2,0262 + 2,2812 = 4,3074$	IV W-T Strategy (Defensive) $0,8365 + 2,2812 = 3,1177$
Religious and Historical Tourism Objects		
Opportunity (O)	(I) S-O Strategy (Aggressive) $1,0232 + 2,8579 = 3,8811$	(III) W-O Strategy (Turn-Around) $2,3848 + 2,8579 = 5,2427$
Thread (T)	(II) S-T Strategy (Diversification) $1,0232 + 0,4256 = 1,4488$	(IV) W-T Strategy (Defensive) $2,3848 + 0,4256 = 2,8104$
Culinary and Craft Tourism Objects		
Opportunity (O)	(I) S-O Strategy (Aggressive) $2,2652 + 2,2058 = 4,471$	(II) W-O Strategy (Turn-Around) $0,6320 + 2,2058 = 2,8378$
Thread (T)	(III) S-T Strategy (Diversification) $2,2652 + 0,7225 = 2,9877$	(IV) W-T Strategy (Defensive) $0,6320 + 0,7225 = 1,3545$

Source: research in 2021

Based on Table 5, it is recommended to use the following:

- a. Quadrant I, namely the Growth-Oriented strategy with the S-O main strategy in the Development of Natural tourism objects.
- b. Quadrant 2, namely the Turn Around strategy, reverses negative trends into positive ones in the development of Cultural tourism objects.
- c. Quadrant 3, namely the Aggressive Maintenance strategy (aggressive repair strategy) in developing Religious and Historical tourism objects.
- d. Quadrant 1, namely the Growth-Oriented strategy (fast-growth strategy) in developing Culinary and Craft tourism objects.

4. Singkarak Lake Tourism Object Cluster Analysis

The clustering of Singkarak Lake tourism objects using Quartile and Hierarchical Cluster analysis techniques in 19 villages based on data obtained by IFAS and EFAS is shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Weight of Tourism Objects in Each Singkarak Lake Tourism Area

No	Tourism Village	Natural Tourism	Cultural Tourism	Culinary Tourism	Craft Tourism	Religious Tourism	Historical Tourism
1	Paninggahan	0.3904	0.5996	0.7452	0.4199	0.5904	0.3078
2	Muaro Pingai	0.0808	0.3588	0.5728	0.1284	0.3012	0.0842
3	Sandiang Baka	0.2742	0.3115	0.2769	0.1084	0.3488	0.3252
4	Sumani	0.0814	0.4268	0.2667	0.1435	0.3400	0.0230
5	Koto Sani	0.1658	0.4295	0.2502	0.2007	0.2058	0.2305
6	Singkarak	0.2922	0.3884	0.1534	0.1136	0.1986	0.2163
7	Aripan	0.1433	0.2842	0.2484	0.0958	0.1914	0.1899
8	Tikalak	0.2226	0.3130	0.1498	0.0389	0.1713	0.1068
9	Kacang	0.2517	0.4062	0.1246	0.0288	0.3008	0.1652
10	Tanjung Alai	0.1863	0.2567	0.0552	0.0205	0.1860	0.2207
11	Sumpur	0.3426	0.5485	0.0540	0.2163	0.1234	0.1136
12	Batu Taba	0.2268	0.4395	0.7488	0.1899	0.0503	0.0958
13	Guguk Malalo	0.4024	0.4484	0.3900	0.1068	0.7556	0.4389
14	Padang Laweh Malalo	0.3692	0.3772	0.2607	0.0652	0.7048	0.3288
15	Simawang	0.3888	0.3516	0.2529	0.1078	0.6700	0.2814
16	Rambatan	0.3868	0.5169	0.2502	0.1842	0.3972	0.2658
17	Balimbing	0.2553	0.2193	0.1578	0.0252	0.2169	0.2268
18	Padang Magek	0.2514	0.2678	0.1454	0.0230	0.1134	0.2295
19	Tigo Koto	0.3372	0.2346	0.2223	0.0252	0.1854	0.2884

Source: Research in 2021

a. Quartile Analysis

The initial stage is the formation of area clusters based on the contribution value of each tourism object using the description of quartile analysis output. Table 7 shows the Quartile analysis calculation results of the data above.

Table 7: Description of Quartile Analysis Output

Tourism Objects	Contribution Value (%)	
	Low	High
Natural Tourism Objects	≤ 0,4658	0,4659 – 0,7904
Cultural Tourism Objects	≤ 0,1265	0,1266 – 0,2139
Religious Tourism Objects	≤ 0,1084	0,1085 – 0,1272
Historical Tourism Objects	≤ 0,0986	0,0987 – 0,1079
Culinary Tourism Objects	≤ 0,2186	0,2187 – 0,3167
Craft Tourism Objects	≤ 0,1158	0,1159 – 0,1854

Source: Research in 2021

b. Hierarchical Cluster

The clustering results of tourism object areas are based on the output of Hierarchical Cluster analysis oriented to ease access, availability of labor, and supporting infrastructure. Based on the dendrogram and orientation, a cluster of Singkarak Lake tourism object areas can be made as shown in Table 8:

Table 8: Clusters of Singkarak Lake Tourism Object Development Areas

Area	Tourism Object	Village	Characteristics
Western Area of Singkarak Lake	Natural Tourism Objects	Paninggahan, Padang Laweh Malalo, Batu Tabu, and Guguk Malalo	tourism objects with the characteristics of natural beauty
Eastern Area of Singkarak Lake	Culinary Tourism Objects	Simawang, Sumpur, Kacang, Tikalak, and Singkarak	tourism objects with the characteristics of artisans and culinary residents
	Craft Tourism Objects	Koto Sani, Aripin, and Tigo Koto	
Northern Area of Singkarak Lake	Cultural Tourism Objects	Padang Magek, Balimbing, and Tanjung Alai	tourism objects with the characteristics of cultures
Southern Area of Singkarak Lake	Religious Tourism Objects	Sandiang Baka and Rambatan	tourism objects with an orientation to the existence of religion and history
	Historical Tourism Objects	Muaro Pingai and Sumani	

Source: Research in 2021

Discussion

The development and identification of Lake Singkarak tourist objects, where there are 19 natural and attractive natural tourist objects, there are also 16 original traditional cultural tourism objects, and there are also 17 religious and historical tourism objects, and there are many culinary and handicraft tourism objects with local flavor and aroma.

Internal factors that support the tourism object of Lake Singkarak, especially the beauty of the beach and its beautiful nature, the presence of unique pandemic fish, *mystacoleucus padangensis* fish species, or non-existent fish found in other areas. There are many interesting and exciting natural phenomena, stable river water sources, safe and comfortable environments, strategic environmental support functions, beach bathing, diving, rowing boats, gliding, hiking, rafting, and various natural attractions. Cultural tourism objects, religious tourism objects, historical tourism objects, handicraft tourism objects, and culinary tourism objects.

Religious and historical tourism objects that are visited by many tourists are the surau and the grave of inyik junjung sirih in rimbo Hulu paninggahan, the cemetery of the grave of syeh anku dubelas in malalo, the Tuo Mosque of Nagari Padang Magek. Cultural Tourism witnesses the Silat dance event, Sewa Dance, Randai Dance, Plate Dance, Indang Dance, Arakan Talempong, Gendang, seruling sarunai that accompanying the Anak Daro-Marapulai, caranao batiray that contents with betel-nut-sadah-gambir in traditional events at the traditional ceremony of manduduk ninik mamak datuk, manti, panito, and dubalang adat during the marriage of the children of the Minang nephews. Natural tourism panoramic views of Gagauan Peak and panoramic views of Ahmad Sadin Peak, spring baths, Cinangkik, Tanah Merah Tabek,

Gobah Hill, Para Layang, White Sand Beach, Pariangan Beach, Macau Duo Peak, Kincia Kamba Tigo, Aur Duri Peak and Lake Singkarak Hydroelectric Power Plant. Culinary of pangek fish sasau, tapas padeh fish rinuk, fish curry tilan, fried jabuih, fried balingkah fish, fried turik fish and fried and pangek sasau and fish bilih, lamang tapai, abuk cake, garubik, dumplings, atoms, lapek bugih, sunsulung, and other cakes. Mansiang plait woven handicrafts, hats, prayer mats, kampie, unjui, pillows, mattresses and others.

External factors that are supporting are accessibility, namely the ring road of Lake Singkarak is good, public transportation from the city center is smooth, supporting facilities around tourism objects, namely health facilities, communication facilities, hotels/inns already exist and restaurants are widely available. Internal factors that become obstacles/weaknesses are the lack of maintenance and management of public facilities, toilets, parking areas, places to stay, lack of promotion, and a threat to the culinary tourism of Lake Singkarak with the emergence of fast-food restaurants such as Pizza Hut, KFC, catfish pecel and other better tourist spots.

The position of the development of Lake Singkarak tourism objects as shown in figure 1, the position of natural tourism objects and culinary-handicraft tourism objects is located in quadrant I which means Aggressive and expansion, this position shows a strong and likely tourism object, a progressive strategy, meaning that it is in prime and steady condition. The

position of cultural tourism objects is located in quadrant II which means diversificationcombination and the position of religious-historical tourism objects are located in quadrant III which means Turn Around and Stability.

The results of the strategic formulation of natural tourism objects and culinary-handicraft with the S-O (strength opportunities) strategy are a Growth Oriented Strategy with a Rapid Growth Strategy, increasing the rate of growth and maximizing the use of all opportunities and the Stable Growth Strategy, maintain existing growth (steady increase, do not let it go down). The formulation of a cultural strategy with the S-T (strength-thread) strategy is a Turnaround strategy, which is a turning strategy to reverse a negative trend to a positive one by the manager and Guirelle strategy, which is to change the function it has with other functions which are completely different and have positive values. Formulation of religious strategies and historical strategies of W-O (weak-opportunities), namely minimizing weaknesses and taking advantage of opportunities with the Aggressive Maintenance Strategy, improving the weaknesses to maximize utilization. Opportunities and Strategies Selective Maintenance strategy is an internal consolidation strategy by maximizing the improvement of weakness factors to take advantage of opportunities.

Clusters of natural, cultural, religious, historical, culinary, and handicraft tourism objects, namely: (1) The cluster of natural tourism object development areas is in the western region of Lake Singkarak, namely Paninggahan Village, Padang Laweh Malalo, Batu Taba, and Guguk Malalo because in the western region there are hills with the majority of the panoramas are interesting; (2) The development cluster for Culinary and Handicraft tourism objects is in the eastern region of Lake Singkarak, namely the Villages of Sumpur, Simawang, Kacang, Tikalak, and Singkarak because the area is supported by the railroad and the Sumatra crossing as well as the number of shops and restaurants where culinary and handicrafts are located; (3) Cluster of Cultural Tourism Objects in the northern region of Lake Singkarak, namely the villages of Padang Magek, Balimbing, and Tanjung Alai, the majority of the people of the region have the expertise and pursue cultural tourism objects and (4) The religious and historical tourism object cluster is located in the southern part of Lake Singkarak, Villages of Sumani, Sandiang Baka, Muaro Pingai, and Rambat. The tourist attraction cluster shows in the map below.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Singkarak Lake consists of 19, 16, 17, 18, 17, and 9 natural, cultural, religious, historical, culinary, and craft tourism objects.
2. The development strategy used is Growth-Oriented for Natural Tourism objects, Turn Around, Aggressive Maintenance, and Growth Oriented for Cultural, Religious and Historical, as well as Culinary and Craft tourism objects.
3. Natural, cultural, religious, and historical as well as culinary and craft tourisms are developed using a Growth (Rapid and Stable) Oriented, S-T (strength-thread) and

Guirelle, W-O (weakness-opportunity), as well as Aggressive and Selective Maintenance strategies, respectively.

The limitation of this research is that it has not been able to determine the superior tourism objects of each cluster. Therefore, further research is recommended to examine the superior tourism objects of each cluster in Singkarak Lake.

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